

Project report: latest enhancements in OpenCitations Meta

Silvio Peroni^{*★} and Elia Rizzetto^{*†}

Introduction

The present document provides a high-level description of the methodology and results of two of the latest extensions made on OpenCitations Meta: the assignment of persistent identifiers to publications containing journal articles (i.e. journal volumes and journal issues) and the support and integration of OpenAlex identifiers for all types of publications.

OpenCitations Meta (OC Meta) (Massari et al. 2024) is the OpenCitations' database for open bibliographic metadata of scholarly publications involved as citing or cited entities in the citations indexed by the OpenCitations infrastructure (Peroni and Shotton 2020) in the OpenCitations Index (OC Index)¹. It presently incorporates basic bibliographic metadata for bibliographic resources (BRs) involved in citations included in the OC Index and recorded in Crossref, DataCite, PubMed, and JaLC, making it the largest bibliographic metadata source using Semantic Web technologies. The bibliographic metadata described in OC Meta includes persistent identifiers (PIDs) such as DOI, PMID, PMCID, ISSN, and ISBN, alongside basic details like title, type, publication date, page range, publication venue, journal volume and issue number/name where applicable. Moreover, OC Meta retains metadata pertaining to responsible agents of each BR (authors, editors, and publishers), along with their PIDs such as ORCID and Crossref ID. Every entity within OC Meta is uniquely identified by the OpenCitations Meta Identifier (OMID), and their properties and relations are specified in compliance with the specifications of the OpenCitations Data Model (OCDM) (Daquino et al. 2020; 2023). Importantly, OC Meta employs Linked Open Data technologies to expose data and provenance information and track data changes. All data within OC Meta is released under a CC0 license. Metadata is accessible through REST API and SPARQL endpoint and periodic data dumps are available in tabular (CSV) and RDF (JSON-LD) formats, generated from a triplestore housing the complete OC Meta graph. Provenance data is only available in the form of RDF (JSON-LD) dumps.

The OpenAlex catalogue (Priem, Piwowar, and Orr 2022), curated and released by OurResearch², emerged following the discontinuation of the Microsoft Academic Graph (MAG) (Sinha et al. 2015). It serves as a comprehensive collection of scholarly metadata encompassing eight distinct entity types: Works (such as journal articles, books, and datasets), Sources (which denote containers like journals, conferences, and repositories), Authors, Publishers, Institutions, Funders, Geo (i.e. geographical data about publications), and Concepts/Topics. The metadata for publications (Work and Source entities) includes external PIDs like DOI, PMID, PMCID, and MAG ID for Works, and ISSN, Wikidata ID, MAG ID, and Fatcat ID for Sources. Each entity within OpenAlex is assigned a

¹ <https://opencitations.net/index>

² <https://ourresearch.org/>

* Research Centre for Open Scholarly Metadata, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna, Bologna, Italy

★ ORCID: 0000-0003-0530-4305

† ORCID: 0009-0003-7161-9310

persistent ID known as the OpenAlex ID. The data is published under a CC0 license and can be accessed through a REST API, a web-based interface, or downloadable snapshots of the entire database in JSON-Lines format.

Objectives and motivation

Created in its first release in December 2022, over the course of the last year OC Meta has undergone major improvements and extensions, some of which are aimed at reaching the objectives described in the present document:

- 1) The use of OMID as a public PID for containers of journal articles, i.e. journal issues and journal volumes, within OC Meta.
- 2) The integration of OpenAlex IDs for bibliographic resources, particularly journals and journal articles, within OC Meta.

As concerns objective 1, it must be mentioned that journal issues and volumes are typically represented only as attributes associated with a journal article rather than entities in their own right. Representing these types of resources as first-class citizens and assigning them a globally unique PID is crucial to ensure compliance with the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016) — thus making their metadata effectively findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. Moreover, their status of first-class entities with a PID allows us to manage provenance information and change-tracking in a consistent way.

Regarding objective 2, adding OpenAlex IDs to the other external identifiers associated with bibliographic resources already registered in OC Meta results in an interlinking between two large open bibliographic metadata collections, OC Meta itself and the OpenAlex catalogue, thus enabling users and systems to interoperably make use of information and functionalities that are specific to either collection. Indeed, OC Meta and OpenAlex, while having several common features, bring each a peculiar contribution to the scholarly metadata landscape. For example, the metadata OpenAlex stores for a publication often goes beyond the basic information that is exposed in OC Meta; on the other hand, OC Meta provides provenance information for all entities and allows for more complex queries by making use of Semantic Web technologies.

Methodology

This section describes at a high level the methodology followed to assign an OMID to journal article containers and to add OpenAlex IDs to existing bibliographic resources.

Methodology for objective 1: OMIDs as PIDs of journal volumes and issues

The process of creating OC Meta (summarised in Figure 1) consists of 2 steps: Curator and Creator. The Curator step takes as input a CSV file in which each row represents a bibliographic resource (e.g. journal article, book, journal) whose metadata are stored in 11 columns, in a linearisation of the OCDM: id, title, author, editor, publication date, venue, volume, issue, page, type, and publisher (Massari and Heibi 2022). The curatorial procedure performed by the Curator step, executed

automatically without the need for human intervention, involves the correction of errors, the standardisation of data format, and the deduplication of metadata entries that correspond to the same entity (by making use of external identifiers, such as DOIs and ISSNs). The output of the Curator step is a curated CSV file that is taken as input by the following step, Creator. Creator takes care of converting the input CSV into OCDM-compliant RDF data, which will then be uploaded to the online triplestore as well as serialised and stored in JSON-LD files. Crucially, in the RDF creation process, OC Meta stores data provenance information and automatically tracks changes: every time an entity is created, modified, merged, or deleted, the details concerning such modifications (primary source, date of modification, responsible agent) are recorded in RDF (and saved to JSON-LD files).

The process of giving a PID to journal volumes and journal issues happens during the Curator step, which includes functionalities to extract journal volumes and journal issues entities from input CSV files and assign them an OMID. As a first step, the software normalises the strings stored in the two dedicated fields of the input CSV, namely “volume” and “issue”. Normalisation operations are executed to correct errors consisting of cases such as volume and issue for a resource being both specified in the same field; prefix or suffix being mistakenly included in the string representing the volume/issue; encoding errors; the issue being misplaced in the volume field, and/or vice versa³ (for more on the error correction procedure, see Massari et al. 2024, 13).

After the normalisation, there is a deduplication phase. While processing a CSV input file, the relationships between venues, volumes, and issues encountered during the process are stored in a temporary dictionary. As new rows get processed, the dictionary is updated: if a journal volume/issue already exists in OC Meta, the resource is indicated in the dictionary with the OMID assigned to it in the triplestore; if it is not present in OC Meta and has not already been encountered while processing the current file, a new entity is created (i.e., a new OMID is minted and assigned to the journal volume/issue in the temporary dictionary); if it is not present in OC Meta but has already been encountered in the current CSV file, the OMID by which it is indicated in the temporary dictionary remains the same, and any new containment relationships exposed in the current row are updated. Since a journal volume/issue is never associated with an OMID or an external ID in the input CSV file, the only way to identify it as a specific entity is to make combined use of both the string representing it (e.g. “vol 1”, “Special issue ‘Urban Morphology’”) and the containment relationship with a given venue (i.e. the journal) that is described in the temporary dictionary (for this reason, a CSV row specifying a volume/issue must also specify the venue in order to be valid, otherwise it would not be possible to disambiguate the volume/issue entity).

Once the Curator process is terminated, the Creator step takes care of modelling the data in RDF according to the OCDM, by making use of the new CSV tables and the temporary dictionary produced by the Curator step. For a more comprehensive description of the OC Meta software and dataset, see the appropriate article (Massari et al. 2024) and the documentation on the software’s GitHub repository⁴.

³ A string containing “volume”, “vol”, “original series”, or appropriate translations in various other languages is considered to represent a journal volume. A string containing “issue”, “special issue”, or appropriate translations in various other languages is considered to represent a journal issue.

⁴ https://github.com/opencitations/oc_meta/

Figure 1. OpenCitations Meta workflow. First, the input data in CSV format is automatically corrected (1), deduplicated, and enriched with pre-existing information from within a triplestore (2). The corrected CSV is returned as output (3a). Second, the data are transformed into RDF (3b), saved to file (4a) and finally entered into the triplestore (4b). Image and caption taken from Massari et al. (2024).

Methodology for objective 2: OpenAlex IDs for existing bibliographic resources

In order to add OpenAlex IDs to the external identifiers recorded for the bibliographic resources already present in OC Meta, it is first necessary to align these entities to the corresponding ones inside the OpenAlex catalogue, thus creating an OMID-OpenAlex ID mapping. The mapping process is based on the common presence of external identifiers among the metadata associated with a given publication in the two datasets. For example, the OMID of a journal article in OC Meta is mapped to the OpenAlex ID of the same article in OpenAlex if, and only if, at least one of the external identifiers linked to the OMID (e.g. a DOI) is also linked to the OpenAlex ID. For this reason, it is crucial to note that the identifier schemes supported by OC Meta for bibliographic resources (DOI, PMID, PMCID, ISSN, ISBN, and Wikidata ID) are also supported by OpenAlex, with the exception of ISBN. Moreover, as entities are mapped solely based on external identifiers, without resorting to heuristics concerning other metadata (e.g. the similarity between the titles recorded in the two collections for the same journal article), publications lacking an external ID in OC Meta (or having only an ISBN as their external ID) are never mapped to the corresponding entity in OpenAlex.

The mapping process (summarised in Figure 2) takes as input the CSV dump of OC Meta and a JSON-LD snapshot of the OpenAlex database. Initially, two tables are generated to store the OMIDs and the OpenAlex IDs to align: the first table is created from the CSV dump of OC Meta, and each row in it contains the OMID, external PIDs, and type for each bibliographic resource that has at least one external PID (in this phase, publications lacking external PIDs are filtered out); the second table is derived from the OpenAlex dump, and links each individual external PID in OpenAlex to its corresponding OpenAlex ID. The OpenAlex data table is then converted into a local SQLite database, to allow faster retrieval.

Subsequently, the table containing OC Meta publications to be mapped is processed line by line. Each PID associated with each entity is queried against the database containing PID-OpenAlex ID associations. The output of the mapping process consists of three tables:

1. A table storing OMID, OpenAlex ID, and publication type of those bibliographic resources for which exactly one OpenAlex ID per OMID has been found (i.e. bibliographic resources mapped in a 1:1 ratio).
2. A table storing OMID, OpenAlex IDs, and publication type of those bibliographic resources for which *multiple* OpenAlex IDs per OMID are discovered (multi-mapped bibliographic resources).
3. A table storing OMID and publication type of those bibliographic resources for which no OpenAlex ID was found (non-mapped resources, including only the resources that have at least one external ID in OC Meta).

Figure 2. The process of mapping OMIDs to OpenAlex IDs.

The launch of the mapping process, which works automatically from start to end, can be configured to specify whether *all* publications in the OC Meta CSV should be processed or only those that do

not already have an OpenAlex ID associated with them, so it is easier to re-create a mapping if necessary.

Once the mapping process has successfully terminated, the output tables storing OMIDs and OpenAlex IDs mapped in a 1:1 ratio are minimally adjusted and normalised to be taken as input by OC Meta, which finally adds OpenAlex IDs to the external identifiers already available. We decided to include only OpenAlex IDs that are mapped seamlessly to exactly one OMID to limit the introduction of incorrect data, as we have noticed that multi-mapped resources are often signals of errors and inconsistencies (born in OpenCitations' software, in OpenAlex's software, or propagated directly from the primary sources).

For a detailed analysis of the mapping process, see the related article (Rizzetto and Peroni 2024) and the GitHub repository⁵.

Results

The following subsections illustrate the achieved results for both the main objectives of the project.

Results for objective 1: OMIDs as PIDs of journal volumes and issues

OMIDs of journal volumes and journal issues can be found in the RDF data dump of OC Meta in JSON-LD format, starting from version 4 (OpenCitations 2023); they are also recorded in the data accessible online via SPARQL endpoint⁶ and REST API⁷.

To date, there are 2,114,595 journal volumes and 5,537,008 journal issues in the OC Meta triplestore, each with its own OMID. The number of journal issues and journal volumes currently available in OC Meta can be retrieved by querying the SPARQL endpoint at "<https://opencitations.net/meta/sparql>" in the following way (Script 1).

```
PREFIX fabio: <http://purl.org/spar/fabio/>

SELECT (COUNT (?br) AS ?count) {
  ?br a fabio:JournalVolume.
}
```

Script 1. SPARQL query to retrieve the number of journal volumes (i.e. entities of type fabio:JournalVolume) in the OC Meta triplestore. To retrieve the number of journal issues, run the same query after replacing fabio:JournalVolume with fabio:JournalIssue.

Results for objective 2: OpenAlex IDs for existing bibliographic resources

OpenAlex IDs for bibliographic resources that it was possible to map, including but not limited to journal articles and journals, are provided both in the CSV and the JSON-LD dump files of OC Meta starting from version 8 of the CSV dataset (OpenCitations 2024b) and version 6 of the RDF dataset (OpenCitations 2024a).

To date, there are 82,467,172 bibliographic resources with an OpenAlex ID registered in the OC Meta triplestore, out of 114,621,237 bibliographic resources. The mapping process has taken as

⁵ https://github.com/opencitations/oc_alignoa

⁶ <https://opencitations.net/meta/sparql>

⁷ <https://opencitations.net/meta/api/v1>

input a CSV file with 107,036,234 rows, therefore approximately 77% of processed publications have received their OpenAlex ID. A bibliographic resource might lack an OpenAlex ID in its metadata due to one of the following causes:

- the entry in OC Meta lacks external identifiers also supported by OpenAlex (8,956,239 resources from the CSV file taken as input by the mapping process).
- the entity, despite having OpenAlex-supported external identifiers, has not aligned with any OpenAlex ID by the mapping process (9,673,137 resources, likely provided for the most part by primary sources that are not used by OpenAlex, such as DataCite⁸).
- the entity was not registered in the CSV file processed for the mapping, either due to an error or because it was provided by the primary source after the latest execution of the mapping process (8,667,538 resources from the triplestore, which will receive their OpenAlex IDs in the future versions of OC Meta).
- the entity maps to more than one entity in OpenAlex (184,079 multi-mapped resources from the CSV input of the mapping process, whose OpenAlex IDs have intentionally not been considered for the integration in OC Meta).
- the entity maps to the same OpenAlex ID as at least one other entity in OC Meta, due to the fact that they are associated with the same external ID, e.g. a DOI (5,727,130 resources from the CSV input of the mapping process, essentially duplicates, whose OpenAlex IDs have intentionally not been considered for the integration in OC Meta).

The number of OpenAlex IDs in the OC Meta triplestore can be retrieved by querying the SPARQL endpoint in the following way (Script 2):

```
PREFIX datacite: <http://purl.org/spar/datacite/>

SELECT (COUNT(?identifier) AS ?count)WHERE{
    ?identifier datacite:usesIdentifierScheme datacite:openalex .
}
```

Script 2. SPARQL query to retrieve from the OC Meta triplestore the number of OpenAlex IDs.

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⁸ <https://datacite.org/>

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